

1 Evaluation of influenza A/H3N2 epidemiology in England during the 2 2025-26 season

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14 Abstract

15 England has experienced a high growth rate of infections caused by the influenza A/H3N2 K clade.
16 Antigenic change from the previously dominant clade, a rapid selective sweep evident in genomic
17 data, and an unusually early start to the season have raised concerns about the potential severity of
18 this year's influenza season. We analysed publicly available surveillance data going back to the
19 2011/12 season and found that the peak growth rate of influenza infections and the peak time-varying
20 reproduction number has been largely consistent with previous severe seasons. Scenario analyses
21 using an age-stratified compartmental model compared to the previous A/H3N2 season in 2022/23
22 suggest that current trends are compatible with moderate levels of immune escape in all ages, or
23 slightly greater immune escape in children, or a 10-20% higher R_0 , or an earlier seed date with no
24 change in virus fitness or immune escape. Substantial immune escape appears to be unlikely given
25 current epidemiological trends. In almost all scenarios, an earlier and faster epidemic growth rate
26 leads to earlier depletion of susceptibles with a dampening effect due to the half term school holiday.
27 To support understanding and exploration of model outputs, an interactive visualisation tool was
28 developed and made available online: <https://hay-idd.shinyapps.io/ModelFluUk-H3N2/>. This rapid
29 analysis is intended to support situational awareness. It provides quantitative comparisons of early
30 epidemic growth rates with previous seasons and qualitative insights into plausible epidemic
31 dynamics.

32 **Data availability:** All code and data required to reproduce the analyses are available at
33 https://github.com/hay-idd/influenza_H3N2_k_clade

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47 obtained through routine surveillance using de-identified data.

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54 Introduction

55 The 2025/26 influenza season in the northern hemisphere has been dominated by an antigenically
56 drifted clade of A/H3N2 viruses. This K clade is descended from the J.2 clade on which the vaccine
57 strain selection was based and has swept to dominance from a frequency of <1% on 2025-07-02 to
58 94% in Europe as of 2025-12-13 (1). This suggests a substantial fitness advantage over other J.2
59 viruses (2). The combination of rapid growth, multiple antigenic substitutions in the haemagglutinin
60 (HA) protein, antigenic mismatch with the vaccine strain, typically higher morbidity and mortality
61 amongst the elderly during A/H3N2 seasons (3), and an unusually early start to the season have
62 raised concerns over the potential for a severe season (4–6). Furthermore, the 2025 flu season in
63 Australia was one of the worst on record (7), and Japan suffered from an early epidemic leading to
64 school closures and increased hospitalisations (8).

65 The interaction of season timing, antigenic drift, other subtype dynamics, vaccine efficacy and
66 coverage, non-HA-mediated immunity, immune waning from previous seasons, climate factors, and
67 contact pattern changes around school holidays is complex and leads to highly varied cumulative
68 and peak seasonal burden (9). The potential outlook of the 2025/26 influenza season is therefore
69 uncertain, though historical seasons with early onset have often been severe (3).

70 Real-time epidemiological assessment in England is based on weekly influenza surveillance data
71 from the Second-Generation Surveillance System (SGSS) (10), which compiles respiratory virus
72 testing data from multiple sources: the Royal College of General Practitioners Research &
73 Surveillance Centre (primary care), the Respiratory DataMart system (hospital testing) and other
74 hospital testing. The main surveillance indicator in the UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) weekly
75 surveillance reports is the percentage of all tests in the SGSS which are positive for influenza among
76 all patients presenting with influenza-like illness (ILI). This metric increased much earlier than in other
77 recent seasons and has started declining as of the report published on 2025-12-18 using data up to
78 2025-12-14 (10). An advantage of the percentage positive metric is that it is thought to be less biased
79 by changes in overall testing volume than count data, however, it is also affected by the dynamics
80 of other ILI-causing pathogens. An ILI+ indicator, which multiplies ILI cases by the percentage of
81 tests positive for influenza, is therefore often recommended instead (11). We focus here on influenza
82 case counts and ILI+, both overall and for A/H3N2, and stratified by age for recent years, to
83 understand the transmission rate of the current clade K viruses in England based on traditional
84 measures of absolute growth rate and R_t .

85 We analysed publicly available epidemiological data from England and developed an age-stratified
86 Susceptible-Infected-Recovered model to address two questions:

- 87 1. Do the epidemiological data indicate a more transmissible A/H3N2 strain than previous
88 seasons?

89 2. Under plausible scenarios of a virus with increased transmissibility, earlier seeding, and/or
90 substantial immune evasion, what is the potential impact on cumulative and peak healthcare
91 burden for the rest of the season?
92

93 **Methods**

94 **Epidemiological analyses**

95 **Data summary**

96 We analysed weekly counts of reported influenza cases by subtype for England from the Respiratory
97 DataMart system from 2009-04-27 to 2025-12-08 (**Figure S1**). We also analysed weekly counts of
98 reported influenza specimens stratified by subtype for England from the WHO FluNet platform
99 between 2011-01-09 and 2025-12-14 (12). All data are aggregated by week, and we used the first
100 day of the epidemiological week as the reported date. We removed the most recent week of data to
101 avoid issues arising from reporting delays. As many influenza A cases are not subtyped, we
102 distributed untyped counts into influenza A/H3N2 and A/H1N1pdm09 counts proportional to the
103 ratios of subtyped samples. Further information on all datasets and extraction methods is provided
104 in the **Supplementary Material**.

105 To understand age-specific dynamics, we also used data on influenza cases by age group and by
106 subtype from the Royal College of General Practitioners Research & Surveillance Centre (RCGP
107 RSC) and ILI from the RCGP RSC weekly reports (**Figure S1-3**). Following recommendations from
108 (11), we developed an ILI+ indicator for each age group as:

$$109 \quad ILI_+ = ILI * p_{+ve} * N$$

110 Where p_{+ve} is the proportion of all tests which are positive for influenza either overall or by subtype
111 and N is the number of individuals in that age group. Note that imperfect case ascertainment is
112 implicit in the ILI data.

113

114 **Weekly growth rate calculations**

115 Weekly growth rates were calculated for each influenza season and aligned by calendar week as:

$$116 \quad y = \log\left(\frac{i(t)}{i(t-1)}\right)$$

117 Where $i(t)$ is the reported incidence over week t . We calculated weekly exponential growth rates
118 of influenza cases in England from the Respiratory DataMart using a Gaussian random walk model
119 as described by Eales et al (13). We also calculated overall weekly growth rates using data from
120 the WHO FluNet for comparison using the same method. Finally, we fitted a Generalised Additive
121 Model (GAM) with a thin-plate spline using the *mgcv* R package to describe weekly growth rates of
122 the age-stratified ILI+ data from the RCGP RSC data (14).

123

124 **Time-varying reproduction number estimation**

125 We estimated the time-varying reproduction number (R_t) using the *EpiEstim* package in R (15). R_t is
126 defined as the expected number of new infections at time t , divided by past incidence weighted by
127 relative infectiousness given by the generation interval distribution. We used the overall weekly
128 influenza incidence data for the period 2011/12 season to the 2025/26 from the UKHSA Respiratory
129 DataMart for this analysis. To approximate daily incidence, weekly counts were distributed evenly
130 across days per week and then smoothed with a 14-day rolling mean. The serial interval distribution
131 was assumed to follow a distribution with a mean of 3.6 days and a standard deviation of 1.6 days,
132 based on (16). We used a window size of 14 days and the default Gamma-distributed prior on R_t
133 with a mean of 5 and standard deviation of 5 (15).

134 **Compartmental model and scenario analyses**

135 **Model overview**

136 To explore potential epidemic scenarios distinguishing the current influenza season from the
137 previous A/H3N2 season in 2022/23, we simulated seasonal influenza transmission dynamics for
138 England using an age- and immunity-structured deterministic Susceptible-Infected-Recovered
139 model. We explored scenarios where the K clade viruses exhibit enhanced transmissibility, greater
140 immune escape, or an earlier epidemic seed time. We compared the impact of these scenarios on
141 the epidemic timing around the half-term and Christmas school holidays, the final epidemic size, the
142 final size in 65+ year olds, and peak incidence as a proxy for maximum healthcare burden.

143 **Model structure**

144 We divided the population into four age groups (0-4, 5-18, 19-64 and 65+ years) and two immunity
145 classes (fully susceptible and partially immune), representing eight classes in total.

146 The force of infection in group i was defined as:

147
$$\lambda_i(t) = \beta \sum_{j=1}^m C_{i,j}(t) I_j(t)$$

148 Where β is the overall transmission rate (not age-stratified), $C_{i,j}$ is the contact rate between group i
149 and group j , and I_j is the number of infected individuals in group j at time t . The basic reproduction
150 number, R_0 , was given by the largest eigenvalue of the next-generation matrix with contact matrix
151 C , multiplied by β and the infectious period, T_g .

152 Transition rates between the three compartments were defined by the following set of ordinary
153 differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned} 154 \quad \frac{dS_{a,k}}{dt} &= -\eta_k S_{a,k}(t) \lambda_{a,k}(t) \\ 155 \quad \frac{dI_{a,k}}{dt} &= \eta_k S_{a,k}(t) \lambda_{a,k}(t) - \frac{I_{a,k}(t)}{T_g} \\ 156 \quad \frac{dR_{a,k}}{dt} &= \frac{I_{a,k}(t)}{T_g} \end{aligned}$$

157 Where η_k denotes the relative susceptibility of immune class k and T_g is the infectious period. Note
158 that η_k was set to 0 for the immune population, representing all-or-nothing immunity. Immune escape
159 was modelled as a single parameter, δ , which scales the initial population immune proportion in all
160 age groups ($\delta=0$ corresponds to complete immune escape, whereas $\delta=1$ corresponds to no loss of
161 population immunity). We solved the model in daily timesteps using the *deSolve* R package (17).

162 **Baseline model calibration**

163 Model parameters were chosen based on standard seasonal influenza parameter values (R_0 of
164 around 2, infectious period of 4-5 days, and final size of around 15% (18)). We used our intuition and
165 manual calibration to generate seasonal dynamics similar to what was seen in the 2022/23 season.
166 We note that this is a complex model with a large number of parameters, making formal model fitting
167 difficult. Some of the parameters are hard to identify and interpret, such as the overall fraction of
168 symptomatic cases reported, the symptomatic fraction by age combined with age-specific reporting
169 rates, and the level of immune escape of the seed virus. Parameter values used for the baseline
170 scenario are shown in **Table S1**.

171 We set the population size of the model to 60,000,000 to approximate the population size of England.
172 We distributed the population into age groups based on the age distributions in the *socialmixr*
173 package using the POLYMOD data (19). Each age group was stratified into the susceptible or fully
174 immune class assuming different levels of immune escape for each age group. The epidemic was
175 seeded by arbitrarily setting $I_{19-64}(0) = 1000$; the seed time was varied during model calibration.

176 **Contact matrices over time**

177 Symmetric, age-stratified contact matrices were generated using all contact data from the
178 POLYMOD UK study using the *socialmixr* R package (19). We generated four contact matrices for
179 different time periods: 1) regular school term-time; 2) half-term with no school contacts and reduced
180 school contacts; 3) pre-Christmas shopping period (2022-12-01 to 2022-12-21) with an increase in
181 all non-school contacts; and 4) the Christmas school holiday period (2022-12-21 to 2023-01-05) with
182 no school contacts, a reduction in all contacts, and an increase in at-home contacts. These matrices
183 were constructed by resampling the original POLYMOD contact diary entries with replacement and
184 applying multipliers for home, work and other contact types. We smoothed the transition between

185 contact matrices over 3 days before and after the holiday period using a cosine function. Holiday
186 dates were based on the Oxfordshire school holiday period. For all non-school contacts, the relative
187 changes in contacts over half-term holidays and the Christmas period (shopping and holiday) were
188 extrapolated from 2021-2023 data from Kendall et al. (see Figures 5A and 7B in the paper) (20).
189 Absolute changes in overall non-school contact rates were extrapolated from the same source (see
190 Figures 1A, 7A in the paper).

191 **Scenario analyses**

192 Scenario analyses were chosen to illustrate potential hypotheses for the early and rapid growth of
193 A/H3N2 cases in England for the 2025/26 season. We also varied the immune escape scaling
194 parameter δ , the basic reproduction number R_0 , the proportion of the 0-4 and 5-18 year old
195 population initially immune, and the seed date univariably.

196 **Implementation**

197 All analyses were implemented and run in R version 4.2.2. The compartmental model was also
198 implemented as a Shiny app with user-friendly sliders to change key parameter values, available at:
199 <https://hay-idd.shinyapps.io/ModelFluUk-H3N2/>.

200 **Results**

201 **The maximum growth rates of total and A/H3N2 influenza cases in the current season are** 202 **comparable to previous seasons**

203 We propose the epidemic growth rate as an early indicator of epidemic fitness of an influenza strain,
204 as it is a compound measure of intrinsic transmissibility, R_0 , of immune escape, and of behavioural
205 mixing patterns. The peak growth rate occurs well before the peak of cases, at which point the growth
206 rate is zero.

207 The peak growth rate of all influenza cases combined (i.e., aggregating A/H3N2, A/H1N1pdm09,
208 untyped influenza A, and influenza B) for the 2025/26 season is comparable to previous seasons
209 with a peak value so far (as of 2025-12-08) of 0.651 (posterior mean; 95% credible intervals: 0.470-
210 0.838) in epidemiological week 40 (2025-09-29 to 2025-10-05) (**Figure 1**). The 2014/15, 2017/18,
211 2022/23 and 2023/24 seasons all had higher peak growth rates for influenza cases combined,
212 though the 2023/24 season featured a mixture of subtypes (**Table 1**). The 2025/26 season stands
213 out as an outlier in the timing of peak growth, which occurred in epidemiological week 40. In contrast,
214 all other seasons showed peak growth rates between week 47 and week 51. After aligning the
215 epidemic curves to the date of peak growth rate, overall trends appeared similar (**Figure S4**), though
216 the 2025/26 season has shown a secondary, albeit smaller rise in growth rate matching the timing
217 of other influenza seasons.

218 Restricting our analysis to only influenza A/H3N2 cases gave similar growth rate results, though the
219 2025/26 season was ranked second for peak A/H3N2 growth rate at 0.709 (0.506-0.919), surpassed
220 only by the 2014/15 season which peaked at 0.840 (0.665-1.02). Similar trends were observed using
221 the WHO FluNet data, though with a higher peak growth rate of A/H3N2 (**Figure S5**).

222 We observed higher peak growth rates of all influenza cases in the 0-4 and 5-18 year old age groups
223 compared to individuals aged 65+ (**Figure S6**). The difference in weekly growth rates between
224 children and adults was far higher than has been observed in the prior two influenza seasons, but
225 comparable to the 2022/23 season when A/H3N2 last dominated (**Table 2**).

226

227 **Figure 1. Growth rate estimates of all influenza cases from the UKHSA Respiratory DataMart using a**
 228 **Gaussian random walk model, starting in the 2011/12 season.** Coloured lines and shaded regions show
 229 posterior mean and 95% credible intervals for the model-estimated weekly growth rate. Colouring distinguishes
 230 the current season from post and pre pandemic seasons. Dynamics were severely disrupted during the
 231 COVID-19 pandemic and were thus excluded (2019/20, 2020/21 and 2021/22 seasons). The doubling time
 232 corresponding to the growth rate is shown on the right hand y-axis.

233 **Table 1.** Peak overall influenza and A/H3N2 growth rates starting from the 2011/12 season. Note that
 234 estimates from the COVID-19 era (2019/20, 2020/21 and 2021/22 seasons) have been excluded. Rows are
 235 ordered by decreasing peak overall influenza growth rate.

Season	Dominant subtype	Epi week of peak growth rate (all influenza)	Peak growth rate of all influenza cases	Epi week of peak growth rate (A/H3N2)	Peak growth rate of A/H3N2 cases
2014/15	A/H3N2	50	0.812 (0.637-0.986)	50	0.840 (0.665-1.02)
2017/18	Influenza B	51	0.694 (0.552-0.835)	51	0.618 (0.435-0.804)
2022/23	A/H3N2	50	0.676 (0.592-0.760)	50	0.641 (0.546-0.739)
2023/24	Mixed A/H3N2/A/H1N1pdm09	49	0.665 (0.506-0.823)	49	0.647 (0.481-0.806)
2025/26	A/H3N2	40	0.651 (0.470-0.838)	40	0.709 (0.506-0.919)
2012/13	Influenza B	50	0.634 (0.448-0.822)	50	0.452 (0.195-0.723)
2016/17	A/H3N2	49	0.560(0.377-0.753)	49	0.573 (0.389-0.754)
2024/25	A/H1N1pdm09	47	0.512 (0.372-0.648)	47	0.304 (0.114-0.492)
2011/12	A/H3N2	49	0.482 (0.210-0.765)	49	0.55 (0.252-0.855)
2018/19	A/H1N1pdm09	51	0.474 (0.315-0.635)	51	0.545 (0.316-0.783)
2015/16	A/H1N1pdm09	49	0.375 (0.152-0.596)	1 (2016)	0.280 (-0.0192-0.599)
2013/14	A/H1N1pdm09	50	0.362 (0.116-0.615)	50	0.364 (0.0832-0.673)

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Table 2. Values shown are the absolute difference in the mean estimated peak weekly growth rate of all influenza cases between the shown age group (years of age) and the 19-64 year old age group.

Season	0-4	5-18	65+
2022 to 2023	0.236	0.409	0.169
2023 to 2024	0.052	0.118	0.226
2024 to 2025	0.065	0.194	0.032
2025 to 2026	0.203	0.343	0.116

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241 **Estimates for the time-varying reproduction number are comparable to previous seasons**

242 We used the subtype-specific case counts from the Respiratory DataMart dataset from the 2011/12
243 to 2025/26 season to estimate the time-varying reproduction number, R_t , for the dominant influenza
244 A subtype in each season (**Figure 2, Figure S7**). We compared peak R_t values and dates occurring
245 after at least 2% of the total number of cases for that season had occurred (to ignore early outbreak
246 stochasticity). Peak R_t values occurred in December across all seasons examined, except for the
247 2024/25 season (peak on 2024-11-25) and the 2025/26 season (2025-10-06) . Despite its early start,
248 the 2025/26 season was comparable to previous influenza seasons, with a peak R_t estimate of 1.49
249 (posterior mean; 95% credible intervals: 1.28, 1.71), compared to 1.33 (1.28-1.37) in the 2022/23
250 season, 1.41 (1.27-1.56) in the 2017/18 season, and 1.53 (1.39-1.67) in the 2014/15 season.

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Figure 2: Estimates of the time-varying reproductive number for the dominant influenza A subtype in each season. Solid lines and shaded regions show the mean and 95% confidence intervals calculated using the *EpiEstim* package. The dashed vertical line shows the timing of the peak R_t estimate after at least 2% of total cases had been reported. The inset label shows the date and estimates of that peak R_t estimate. Only data for the dominant influenza A subtype in each season were used, except for the 2023/24 season where both influenza A/H1N1pdm09 and A/H3N2 circulated at high levels. Note that the 2012/13 and 2017/18 seasons were dominated by influenza B.

259 **Scenario analyses using an age-stratified compartmental model**

260 All scenarios are shown in **Figure 3**, with dynamics in the 65+ age group shown in **Figure S8**, and
261 the weekly growth rates of the scenarios shown in **Figure S9**. Although we present individual
262 scenarios in the main text, we also varied each of these key model parameters over a range of values
263 individually (**Figure 4**).

264 Scenarios with increased immunity escape led to an earlier and larger epidemic that could peak in
265 early December (**Table 3; Figure 3**). Reducing the initial proportion of the population in the immune
266 compartment by just 5% (relative to the compartment's size) led to an increase in the overall final
267 size of the epidemic, with cases increasing earlier in the season but still peaking in early December.
268 Larger drops in initial population immunity led to implausibly early and large epidemics, which is
269 inconsistent with current surveillance data, suggesting that the level of immune escape of the K clade
270 strain is likely to have reduced population immunity by no more than 10%.

271 Increased intrinsic transmissibility (proxied by increasing R_0 without changing the population immune
272 fraction) led to an earlier epidemic peak, more cases prior to the Christmas period and a larger final
273 size. Seeding the epidemic earlier led to a more drawn-out epidemic with a lower infection peak, but
274 a very similar final size and timing of the peak.

275 Reducing the immune fraction only in individuals under 18 years of age also led to earlier and larger
276 epidemics, though with a reduced epidemic peak size. A major reduction in immunity in children led
277 to a much longer epidemic duration with peak incidence in October, but a similar total final size and
278 peak size compared to more moderate reductions. Final size in the 65+ group was either similar or
279 reduced. This is likely due to the interaction with the half term period, which acts as a temporary
280 circuit break to dampen the incidence curve.

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Figure 3. Comparison of epidemic trends across different model scenarios varying assumptions around the new A/H3N2 K clade immune escape, transmissibility and seed date. Note that the base case is based on loose visual fitting to the 2022/23 seasonal influenza case data from the RCGP RSC. Dynamics in the 65+ age group only are shown in **Figure S8**. This base scenario should be interpreted with caution as no formal fitting was performed, and thus there is considerable underrepresented uncertainty and risk of poor parameterisation.

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288 **Figure 4. Univariable sensitivity analyses of the model outputs with respect to key parameters.** Each
 289 row shows the impact of varying one parameter, given in the x-axis label, whilst keeping all other parameters
 290 at their baseline values. The vertical dashed line shows the values used for the base scenario. Results shown
 291 are for the epidemic final size (proportion of the population infected) overall and within the 65+ age group, the
 292 peak epidemic growth rate after at least 1% of total infections have occurred, and the peak weekly infection
 293 incidence.

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Table 3. Comparison of peak disease burden and overall disease burden of model scenarios relative to base case. Peak growth rate was taken as the highest overall weekly growth rate after at least 1% of all infections had occurred. All results shown, other than peak growth rate, are based on the ratio of outputs from the scenario to the base case. We do not report absolute numbers due to the lack of formal model fitting (other than the epidemic final size of the base case to roughly guide interpretation of the ratios).

Scenario label	Scenario	Parameters changed from baseline	Peak of weekly symptomatic cases	Date of peak symptomatic cases	Peak growth rate	Date of peak growth rate	Cumulative symptomatic cases	Final size in 65+	Final size	Interpretation
A	Base case (loosely based on the 2022/23 season)	-	1.00	26/12/2022	0.83	05/12/2022	1.00	1.00 (7.57%)	1.00 (16.2%)	Model parameters are roughly calibrated to match the 2022/23 influenza season, but we note that there is considerable hidden uncertainty, strong correlations between model parameters and structural identifiability issues.
B	Moderate immune escape	Immune escape parameter set to 0.95	1.23	12/12/2022	0.70	07/11/2022	1.37	1.51	1.32	A relatively small loss of population immunity leads to a larger outbreak overall.
C	High immune escape	Immune escape parameter set to 0.90	1.39	05/12/2022	0.82	17/10/2022	1.63	1.81	1.54	As in B, but with a much larger overall impact.
D	Severe immune escape	Immune escape parameter set to 0.80	1.94	14/11/2022	1.30	10/10/2022	2.06	2.37	1.89	This can be ruled out, as an extremely large epidemic would have already peaked in November.
E	Severe reduction in immunity in children	All initial immune fractions in <18 year olds reduced by 50%	0.87	17/10/2022	1.71	03/10/2022	1.13	0.77	1.26	Drastically increased transmission in children would lead to a peak before the half-term holiday and the epidemic ending by the New Year. Can be ruled out.
F	Minor reduction in immunity in children	Initial immune fraction in 0-4 reduced to 20%; initial immune fraction in 5-18 reduced to 50%	0.88	05/12/2022	0.82	07/11/2022	1.13	1.00	1.20	Dampens the peak due to the half term circuit break. Leads to higher overall final size and lower burden in older adults. A resurgence after half term is expected.
G	Higher transmissibility	R_0 increased from 1.9 to 2.2	1.04	05/12/2022	0.79	07/11/2022	1.25	1.30	1.22	An increase in final size in all age groups and an early peak, but with a similar peak size.
H	Severe transmissibility	R_0 increased from 1.9 to 2.4	0.99	21/11/2022	1.12	10/10/2022	1.31	1.38	1.28	Similar to G but counterintuitively leads to a more drawn-out epidemic with slightly lower peak incidence. This is likely due to the timing of the half term dampener with respect to incidence, which lessens the overshoot of infections after herd immunity is reached.
I	Two week earlier seeding	Seeding on 2025-08-24 rather than 2025-09-10	0.79	19/12/2022	0.62	05/12/2022	0.99	0.97	1.00	A very similar overall burden of infection and with a much lower peak burden expected in mid-December.
J	One month earlier seeding	Seeding on 2025-08-01 rather than 2025-09-10	0.63	19/12/2022	0.57	03/10/2022	1.00	0.99	1.00	Similar to I, but with an overall peak growth rate seen in the first week of October rather than early December.

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298 Discussion

299 Our analysis shows that the K clade of influenza in England has, as of 2025-12-18, an unusually
300 early peak epidemic growth rate and time-varying reproduction number but of magnitude comparable
301 to previous severe seasons over the past 15 years. The time-varying reproduction number peaked
302 at 1.49 (CI=[1.28,1.71]) on 2025-10-06 based on current data, which is slightly higher than the typical
303 reproduction number of seasonal influenza of 1.2-1.3 reported in the literature (21), but similar to
304 what we estimated using the *EpiEstim* Rpackage for previous seasons. There have been
305 substantially higher growth rates of A/H3N2 cases this season in children <18 years old compared
306 to adults. We also ran scenario analyses to explore possible virus changes which might be
307 compatible with the earlier start to the season. Only small reductions in population immunity due to
308 immune escape are required to drive an earlier influenza season with more cumulative infections
309 (the model parameter δ), suggesting that substantial escape from overall population immunity, not
310 just HA-mediated immunity, is incompatible with current data. Overall, our findings suggest that the
311 total infection burden in England is likely to be at the upper end of typical influenza seasons.

312

313 Antigenic escape from both the vaccine strain and the overall population immune landscape are
314 thought to be predictors of subsequent seasonal influenza burden (9). For the clade K A/H3N2
315 viruses, substantially reduced reactivity of vaccine raised ferret antisera and human sera has been
316 observed (4,22,23). Our scenario analyses suggest that the level of total immune escape in the
317 population is relatively modest, as substantially greater immune escape would generate an even
318 earlier start and markedly higher peak growth rates than those observed.

319

320 For seasonal influenza, which is likely driven by high within-age-group social mixing and greater
321 susceptibility to infection in children, changes in contact patterns during school term times and
322 holidays have a major impact on the shape of the epidemic (24). Although these changes are difficult
323 to parameterise, our base model likely represents realistic shifts in behaviour (20). Whether a new
324 strain with enhanced transmissibility or immune escape will lead to a higher winter burden partially
325 depends on the timing of peak transmission relative to school holidays – the half-term holiday can
326 act as a circuit breaker, dampening the peak and spreading cases over a longer period.

327 The analyses performed here are relatively straightforward and quick, using data which are already
328 routinely collected. Although these types of analyses were used widely during the COVID-19
329 pandemic, they have since become less common for seasonal respiratory diseases. We suggest
330 that real-time growth rate characterisation and public, interactive tools for ongoing scenario analyses
331 should be maintained regularly and updated early in the season to rule in or out different scenarios.
332 Maintaining the toolkit requires low resource but consistent input from technical specialists, and real-

333 time access to absolute reported case numbers rather than just percentage of tests positive for
334 influenza.

335 Our analyses have several limitations. For the epidemiological analyses, we used multiple data
336 sources each with limitations in representativeness and reporting algorithms. Growth rate and R_t
337 estimates are also likely biased by changes in testing intensity and reporting rates. We note that
338 overconfident estimates from small sample sizes are a known issue with renewal equations, affecting
339 especially pre-season estimates when case numbers are very low (25).

340 The model used for scenario analyses is also caveated, as we did not perform a formal model fit due
341 to time constraints. Instead, we chose fixed parameter values based on commonly assumed
342 influenza parameters (R_0 , infectious period, final size), and then manually calibrated other
343 parameters to achieve a reasonable visual fit to the 2022/23 influenza incidence data. Assumptions
344 regarding age-specific immunity, immune escape, and all-or-nothing immunity in two classes rather
345 than stratified immunity all have a large impact on the projected incidence curves (26), and we
346 therefore recommend using the tool to inform a general understanding of the system rather than
347 predictions. A key omission is vaccination, which we did not include in the scenario model due to
348 challenges in parameterising age-specific vaccine efficacy against infection and disease. Our model
349 is also limited using outdated contact data and strong assumptions surrounding behaviour changes
350 in school holidays and the Christmas period. Although we are confident that these assumptions
351 capture general trends, more recent and well-calibrated parameter values would improve the
352 accuracy of the analysis. Finally, we did not consider seasonal forcing due to climate factors (27,28).

353 In summary, we have combined publicly available influenza data for England with an age-stratified
354 Susceptible-Infected-Recovered model and an interactive visualisation webtool. Our analysis shows
355 that compared to previous years, the epidemic growth rate is high but not exceptional. Modelling
356 analysis suggests that the epidemic trajectory so far is consistent with at most modest reduction in
357 population immunity compared to previous years. Increases in transmission do not always translate
358 to bigger epidemics because of the interaction between epidemic dynamics and school holidays that
359 prevent epidemic 'overshoot'. We provide a range of scenarios and an interactive scenario-explorer
360 app, that show the impact of different assumptions on the epidemic curve for the coming months.

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446

447 **Supplementary Material**

448 **Supplementary Methods – additional information on data sources**

449 **1. Second-Generation Surveillance System (SGSS)**

450 Weekly influenza positivity from PCR tests by age was obtained from the UKHSA dashboard for the
451 SGSS, available at [Influenza | UKHSA data dashboard](#). Values are shown as a percentage of people
452 with at least one positive PCR result for influenza (in a 7 day period). Further details are available at
453 [Data quality report: national flu and COVID-19 surveillance report - GOV.UK](#) (1). This dataset
454 provided us with the proportion of tests which are positive for influenza, but not the absolute number
455 of tests performed, proportion positive stratified by influenza subtype, nor stratification by age.

456 **2. Royal College of General Practitioners (RCGP) Research & Surveillance Centre (RSC)**

457 The RCGP RSC is a nationally representative primary care-based surveillance system. Weekly
458 communicable and respiratory diseases reports are publicly available at [RSC: Public health data](#)
459 (2). In theory, this dataset has all of the information needed to construct an ILI+ indicator, but it is
460 only publicly available in PDF reports and a live dashboard. The PDF reports did not contain the
461 granularity required for the full age-stratified ILI+ indicator, and we were unable to automate
462 digitisation of the dashboard.

463 We compiled weekly national incidence of influenza-like illness (ILI) rates (per 100,000 population)
464 for England. PDF reports were downloaded for six-month intervals from January 2021 to
465 December 2025, and Table E from each report was converted to CSV. These tables included age-
466 stratified ILI rates across four age categories differing by reporting period:

- 467 1. 1-4 yrs, 5-14yrs, 15-64yrs and 65+yrs, and all ages from week 26, 2023 to week 44, 2025
- 468 2. <15 yrs, 15-64yrs, 65+yrs, and all ages for weeks 40-53, 2020, week 1, 2021 to week 5,
469 2021, and weeks 1-26, 2023.

470 This dataset provides ILI rates by age, which we convert to estimates for absolute ILI case numbers
471 by multiplying by the population size per age group. However, it does not stratify ILI into influenza
472 A/H3N2 positivity.

473 We also digitised data on the total number of samples tested and the number of samples positive for
474 influenza by age group and by subtype for the 2022/23 to 2025/26 influenza seasons.

475 **3. Respiratory DataMart sentinel system for hospital testing.**

476 The Respiratory DataMart is a sentinel laboratory surveillance system which monitors all major
477 respiratory viruses in England, compiling data from 17 contributing laboratories. Participating
478 laboratories test swabs for respiratory viruses, including influenza A viruses, using real-time
479 polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR), though not all laboratories test for or report all viruses. The
480 absolute number of samples in this system is much lower than SGSS, but gives absolute numbers
481 of tests rather than just percentage positive.

482 We created a combined dataset spanning the period 27 April 2009 to 8th December 2025. This
483 dataset included weekly counts of laboratory-confirmed influenza cases by subtype: influenza A
484 (not subtyped), influenza A(H1N1)pdm09, influenza A(H3N2), and influenza B. Additionally, the
485 dataset provides the overall percentage of specimens testing positive for influenza. However, these
486 datasets were not stratified by age group.

487 **4. World Health Organisation (WHO) FluNet**

488 Weekly counts of reported influenza specimens were obtained from the WHO FluNet platform (3).
489 This is the global influenza virological surveillance system collecting weekly sentinel and non-
490 sentinel (e.g., outbreak investigations, point-of-care testing) surveillance data from national
491 influenza centres. Data was extracted for the period 9th January 2011 to 14th December 2025,
492 restricted to England. The extracted dataset included the weekly number of samples classified as
493 A(H3), influenza A (not subtyped), A(H1N1)pdm09 influenza B, and overall influenza cases. We
494 allocated the unsubtyped influenza A cases into A/H3N2 and A/H1N1 cases proportional to the
495 ratio of subtyped samples.

496 **Aligning mismatched age groups from different datasets**

497 Where age groups were misaligned, we re-distributed metrics (such as ILI or percentage positive
498 for influenza) into new age bandings by assuming that each metric is the same for all ages (in
499 years) within an age group. We then recombined datasets into new age bands by reweighting
500 these age metrics based on the age distribution of England (4).

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515 **Table S1.** Model parameters assumed for the baseline scenario. These are the default parameters
 516 in the interactive web tool.

Parameter	Assumed value
R_0 : basic reproduction number	1.9
T_g : infectious period	4.5 days
γ : immune escape multiplier	1
Seed date	19th September
Seed size in age group 1 (0-4 yrs)	1000
Population size	60,000,000
Proportion of work contacts kept in school holidays	0.75
Multiplier for home contacts in school breaks	1.00
Multiplier for non-school and non-work contacts in school breaks	1.10
Multiplier for all non-school contacts in Christmas period (1-15 December)	1.25
Proportion of all contacts kept over Christmas	0.70
Multiplier for home contacts over Christmas holiday	3.00
Proportion initially immune (0-4 yrs)	0.35
Proportion initially immune (5-18 yrs)	0.60
Proportion initially immune (19-64 yrs)	0.70
Proportion initially immune (65+ yrs)	0.70
Symptomatic fraction and reporting rate (0-4 yrs)	0.05
Symptomatic fraction and reporting rate (5-18 yrs)	0.20
Symptomatic fraction and reporting rate (19-64 yrs)	0.30
Symptomatic fraction and reporting rate (65+ yrs)	0.50

517

518

519 **Figure S1. Comparison of the three data sources used in the analyses for all influenza cases.** RCGP =
 520 Royal College of General Practitioners Research & Surveillance Centre. UKHSA = Respiratory DataMart
 521 system. The top panel shows all data. Bottom panel zooms in on the period since 2025-01-01.

522

523 **Figure S2. Comparison of the three data sources used in the analyses for influenza A/H3N2.** RCGP =
 524 Royal College of General Practitioners Research & Surveillance Centre. UKHSA = Respiratory DataMart
 525 system. The top panel shows all data. Bottom panel zooms in on the period since 2025-01-01.

527

528 **Figure S3. Comparison of age-stratified influenza surveillance indicators.** Indicators: influenza-like-
 529 illness, influenza confirmed cases, and influenza A/H3N2 confirmed cases (ILI+). Data was obtained from the
 530 RCGP RSC.

531

532 **Figure S4. Growth rate estimates of all (A) and A/H3N2 (B) influenza cases from the UKHSA**
 533 **Respiratory DataMart using a Gaussian random walk model, starting in the 2011/12 season and**
 534 **aligned by date of peak growth rate.** Estimates are identical for **Figure 1** but shifted to align the date of
 535 peak growth rate. Coloured lines and shaded regions show posterior mean and 95% credible intervals for the
 536 model-estimated weekly growth rate. Colouring distinguishes the current season from post and pre pandemic
 537 seasons. Dynamics were severely disrupted during the COVID-19 pandemic and were thus excluded
 538 (2019/20, 2020/21 and 2021/22 seasons). The doubling time corresponding to the growth rate is shown on
 539 the right hand y-axis. Seasons are labeled where the peak weekly growth rate exceeded 0.6.

540

541 **Figure S5. Growth rate of influenza cases from the WHO FluNet database.** (A) All influenza cases. (B)
 542 A/H3N2 cases. Coloured lines and shaded regions show posterior mean and 95% credible intervals for the
 543 model-estimated weekly growth rate. Colouring distinguishes the current season from post, pre and during
 544 pandemic seasons. Doubling time is shown on the right hand y-axis.

545

546

547 **Figure S6. Growth rate estimates of age-stratified A/H3N2 cases from the ILI+ indicator.** Shown are the
548 empirical growth rates and model fits using the GAM. School holidays are marked with grey bars. The
549 autumn half-term break (i.e., the recent school holiday) is marked in red. Solid lines and ribbons show mean
550 estimates and 95% confidence intervals.

Dominant influenza A subtype — A/H1N1pdm09 — A/H3N2

551

552 **Figure S7. Daily incidence data used for R_t estimation in Figure 2.**

553

554 **Figure S8. Comparison of symptomatic influenza incidence in 65+ from the scenario analyses shown**
 555 **in Figure 4.**

556

557 **Figure S9. Comparison of weekly age-stratified growth rates from scenarios matching Figure 4.**